

IMPORTANT FACTORS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL COMPETENCE IN PROFESSIONAL EFFECTIVENESS

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Annotation. This article discusses the content of the concept of psychological competence, its components and importance in professional activity. The study analyzed the role of psychological competence as an important factor in increasing the effectiveness of professional activity. In particular, it was shown that factors such as self-awareness, emotional stability, stress resistance, communicative culture and psychological adaptation in problematic situations are of great importance for the successful conduct of a specialist's work.

Key words: *social psychology competence, psychological competence, competence, knowledge, socio-psychological competence, self-awareness, emotional stability, empathy, conflicts, stress tolerance, communicative culture, problem situation.*

In order to be competitive in the modern labor market and achieve high efficiency in professional activities, a specialist must have not only knowledge and skills related to his profession, but also a level of socio-psychological competence. This competence includes the ability of a person to behave correctly towards others, communicate effectively, work in a team, resolve conflicts and adapt to the social environment.

Currently, competence is mainly considered as a human ability, which allows us to think about various human abilities and talents. In this regard, we see that there are different approaches to the interpretation of the concept of “ability”.

In the functional-genetic approach: “ability is interpreted as a description of the efficiency of functional systems that implement a particular mental process. In this case, the concepts of competence and competence, reflecting the combination of

motivational, behavioral and cognitive components in the structure of the individual, can be considered as abilities”.

A.I.Subetto: “the concepts of competence and competence are studied within the framework of the categories of quality, property, skill”. He notes that the concepts of competence and competence are a complex structural and dynamic educational process, but are secondary to the categories of quality and property. This, in turn, is subject to the following general principles:

- the principle of integrity and systematicity, which is based on the internal structure of quality;

- the quality of the object at a high level of quality, and the external structure of quality determines the quality of the interaction of the object or process with the external environment at a real level of quality;

- the principle of the existence of a system of potential and actual external and internal contradictions in the emergence and development of quality;

- the principle of reflecting the quality of various processes in the results.

In his scientific research, A.V.Khutorsky emphasizes that “competence is a manifestation of a specific individual-psychological characteristic, while competence consists of predetermined social requirements for the preparation necessary for a person's effective and high-quality activity in a specific environment”.

In our opinion, competence is not only an individual-psychological characteristic, but also includes emotional-volitional qualities. If it were not for these emotional-volitional qualities, a person would not be able to effectively organize his professional activities.

Important factors of psychological competence in the effectiveness of professional activity

In modern society, the professional success of each specialist is significantly influenced not only by professional knowledge and skills, but also by the level of psychological competence. Psychological competence includes such abilities as the ability of a specialist to understand himself and others, to manage emotional states, to

show flexibility in stressful and problematic situations. This, in turn, is an important factor in increasing the effectiveness of professional activity.

The concept of psychological competence

Psychological competence is the ability of a person to manage his internal state and relationships with others. This competency includes: self-awareness, emotional stability, stress tolerance, making the right decisions in problematic situations, effective communication, etc. If a specialist has these skills, he or she can perform professional tasks with high quality, work effectively with a team and successfully overcome difficult situations.

Important factors of psychological competence in professional activity

1. Self-awareness and management

A specialist must be able to correctly assess his mental state, emotions and control his emotions at the right time. This self-management reduces professional stress and increases work efficiency.

2. Emotional stability

Professional activity is often associated with high pressure and stress, and the emotional stability of a specialist plays a decisive role in the successful performance of his duties.

3. Stress tolerance

The ability to withstand stress allows you to continue working in difficult working conditions without interruption and effectively. This skill is important in overcoming difficulties that arise at work.

4. Communicative culture

Effective communication, the ability to clearly express thoughts and listen to others are one of the main aspects of professional activity. This factor is very important in teamwork and leadership.

5. Psychological adaptation in problem situations

Competence is the manifestation of one's theoretical and practical knowledge, skills and abilities, worldview, beliefs and all personal individual socio-psychological qualities. One of the important factors ensuring the quality and effectiveness of activity

is its competence in its field. It is manifested on the basis of the system of adaptation of activity. These are:

- scientific knowledge;
- epistemological knowledge;
- ability to perform professional activities with competence, efficiency, skill;
- creative approach to finding an effective solution to any problem situations;
- demonstration of high socio-psychological characteristics in the process of activity;
- continuous self-development through the study of one's intellectual, cognitive, emotional, moral potential and the effective use of one's work psychological reserve.
- positive emotional attitude towards society and people, nature and existence is the experience of transitioning to positive thinking.

We can evaluate the following competencies as the main core competencies that students should form in the process of their activities:

- Communicative;
- Self-development as a person;
- Socially active citizenship;
- General culture;
- Being aware of innovations in their field;
- Ability to apply psychodiagnostics in practice.

Flexibility and a creative approach are necessary to successfully resolve conflicts and problems that arise during professional activity.

In conclusion, we can say that psychological competence is an important factor ensuring the effectiveness of professional activity. Self-awareness, emotional stability, stress resistance and effective communication skills of a specialist determine his success in work. Therefore, it is necessary to pay special attention to the development and strengthening of psychological competence in any profession. When studying the process of influence of personal characteristics on the manifestation of socio-psychological competence in students, it became clear that while both phenomena show a positive correlation at some points, in some cases a negative correlation is also

noticeable. These indicators confirm that the uniqueness of individual psychological characteristics of a person can directly affect the emergence of socio-psychological competence in students.

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